

**FORMATION OF DISCIPLINARY ATTITUDE IN STUDENTS AS SOCIAL AND
PEDAGOGICAL NEEDS**

*Ch. Asadova*¹, *S. Istamkulov*², *Sh. Tukhtanazarov*³

Abstract:

The article based on an analysis of the ideas of various specialists gaming technologies and their significance in the development of modern teenager.

Key words: culture, game, question, actions, principles and concepts

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Culture, discipline and education create a person. Culture and education are the experience, the history of the past years, the measurement of everything created by man, and discipline is the recreation of experience in the mind of the younger generation. One of the important parts of culture is a significant social tool – education. In the course of the development of education, it is impossible not to notice that it has accumulated a sufficient number of ways to relay cultural ideas, principles and concepts. These methods are used in practice in working with young people who acquire their own ethno-cultural experience. Consequently, education and discipline play a huge role in the upbringing and development of a modern teenager.

The game is an end-to-end mechanism of child development, through which the contents of all educational areas of the education program are implemented. This contributes to the development of the use of gaming technologies in educational institutions. Children imitate adult relationships, imitate their behavior, most often this is a children's game. One of the important questions of game theory is the question of its historical origin. Psychologist author of original books on psychology and pedagogy – D. B. Elkonin, expresses the opinion that the game could have appeared when the historical development of society determined the role of the child in the system of public relations. As a result of the appearance of complex forms of division of labor, a game arises, the child can no longer work, it will not be possible to attach him to productive labor. The main source of the development of consciousness in children, the unreasonableness of their actions, the behavior of children with adults and peers is the game. When a child takes on a certain role, he tries to fulfill all the rules provided for a specific role, the child tries to change your behavior and make it as close as possible to the rules of this game. The incentive to play in the activity itself. The main component of the game is the role. There are also: the device (structure) of the game, the use of game items and the relationship between players. The plot and content are also components of the game. The plot is a set of actions that the child reflects in the game. And the relationships carried out

¹ *Asadova Ch.S., Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

² *S.Istamkulov, c*

³ *Sh. Tukhtanazarov, Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

by a child between players or adults will be called content. The game usually involves several people, which means the character will be a group. A group of children playing acts in relation to each individual participant as an organizing principle, authorizing and supporting the fulfillment of the role taken by the child. One of the variants of the appearance of the game is an attempt to get rid of free time and creating a pleasant and proper pastime for people. Culture as a "socially progressive creative activity of mankind aimed at transforming reality, transforming the wealth of human history, the inner wealth of the individual, the full identification and development of essential human forces" is characterized as a harmonious balance of spiritual and material values.

The creation of material goods is aimed at serious utilitarian activity. The motive of the game is the process, not the result. This does not imply any material interest. "Liberation from direct need, from work, a person begins to think, feel and create freely, obeying only the thirst of every part of his body – to turn around" – this is what happens to people who are in a real game. It is from the very process of the game that he gets satisfaction. The ancient Greeks believed that "the gods come to the human game and stay in it," being the players patronizing them. The cult community was united in a game, the representative function of which was performed in two ways: the figure of the game world replaced something supernatural, super real, and the scenery — the whole Universe. This attitude to the game gave it the status of divine, superhuman. In this context, F. Nietzsche speaks about the essence of human culture based on the ideal of the spirit playing "with everything that has hitherto been considered sacred, good, inviolable, divine." Using over the real status of the game and the emotional state of the players, the authorities Ancient Greece, Ancient Rome had the opportunity to manipulate individual and mass consciousness for their own purposes. It was possible to show that a person is important to society, has a certain power through attending sports competitions; the stronger ones participated in gladiator fights. As for the spiritual sphere, dancing and music were a sign of the elite. By staying in the game, elite society and representatives of the authorities declared their superhuman status. The secular style of art manifested itself in music, architecture, literature and other forms of art.

In conclusion, the game as a form of human activity has been the subject of philosophical analysis by many philosophers. Common games are very simple, they are similar to animal games: games in which you need to run after each other, catch each other, there are also games with climbing trees or jumping.

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